

Using and understanding the *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid*

Things you should read before	3
1. Purpose of the FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid	3
2. FAIR principles in a nutshell	3
3. Files helping you do the FAIR self-assessment	5
Things you may read at some point	6
1. Time and effort required	6
2. Hints about FAIRness	6
The FAIR principles in context	6
Data and publication	7
The process of FAIR-ification	7
Unfairness of the FAIR principles?	8
3. Additional information	9
Standards	10
Policies	11
Requirements	11
Technologies	11
Things you can read if you really want to	11

This document has been produced within the CRAFT-OA Horizon Europe project by the Aix-Marseille University / OpenEdition team.

CRAFT-OA is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101094397. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The document is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Things you should read before

1. Purpose of the FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid

The *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* is meant to help either publishers or publishing services to start and achieve a self-assessment of their data collections according to the [FAIR principles](#). The final goal is to increase the data and metadata quality of their contents so that they become more easily and more broadly discoverable.

As a self-assessment tool, the *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* does not include any evaluation, especially no automated evaluation of the assessment. It instead supports a manual, but guided, adapted, and open assessment of the FAIR principles implementation.

The reasoning behind this choice is that automated evaluations tools, although useful for other purposes, produce statistical results that are not in themselves self-explanatory, and do not describe what are the FAIRification challenges and opportunities for a specific collection of contents or for a specific publishing system.

In that sense, the *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* has to be considered rather as a management tool fostering awareness of FAIR principles, understanding of their logic, and planning of future FAIR-ification actions. It is also a tool that supports collaboration within a team or between teams, allowing to share common knowledge, terms and perspectives.

The *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* is open insofar as the perimeter of the assessed dataset, the granularity of the review, and the duration of the assessment depends on the needs and priorities of the persons conducting the assessment. Indeed, FAIR principles are only principles, and their application, as well as their assessment, is necessarily contextual. Even more so, FAIRification is a process that may go through several phases over time, and the self-assessment step is a good way to anticipate them. What matters is that, in the end, the FAIR principles are increasingly followed.

The *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* stems from a prior fruitful experiment conducted at [OpenEdition](#), a French Research Infrastructure managing four publication platforms in the Social Sciences and Humanities fields. The experiment proved to be useful to review all datasets carefully and to establish from there a detailed plan of actions for updating datasets, metadata sets, and even the information system itself. Although pretty simple in its design, the *Self-assessment grid* seemed therefore to be, after some adjustments and enhancements, an efficient tool for any organization having similar goals.

FAIR-ification does not happen in one day, it's a journey, and you are already on the road!

2. FAIR principles in a nutshell

The FAIR principles - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability - are guidelines whose aim is to improve the management of digital scholarly resources for both

humans and machines. The principles define the characteristics that enable discovery and reuse of data and, more broadly, any type of digital research object. They assist different research actors to assess and increase the degree of FAIRness of their data. The barriers to the FAIR principles' implementation remain low: the principles are concise, domain-independent, and high-level. The constitutive elements are related, yet separable, and they can be combined in different ways.

Besides the 4 foundational FAIR principles, there are in total 15 detailed sub-principles.

The *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* helps you understand the fully detailed FAIR principles, so there is no need to describe them more in detail here. However, here is a table summarizing the principles in one place:

Code	Principle
F1	(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
F2	Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below).
F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.
F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
A1.1	The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
A2	Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.
I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
I3	(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.
R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.
R1.3	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

3. Files helping you do the FAIR self-assessment

We organized the FAIR principles into a table which can be seen as a grid for a detailed analysis. This *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* should help you conduct the FAIR self-assessment of your contents.

To conduct the review, you will only need the following three files, all based on the same grid:

- the Guidelines file, containing explanations about each FAIR principle;
- the Template file, which is an empty file for you to fill;
- the Example file, containing the example of FAIR self-assessment conducted for the OpenEdition Journals platform (OEJ).

The **Guidelines** file is structured in the following way:

- short introduction about the general FAIR principle;
- detailed description of each sub-principle, itself containing these elements:
 - Generic guidelines for any research digital object;
 - Publishers guidelines for the application of the sub-principle to publications;
 - FAIR review specific objectives for the considered sub-principle.

The **Template** file contains the same grid, but without the guidelines.

The Template comprises three cells on each principles for you to fill:

- FAIR implementations: list here what concretely matches the sub-principle's recommendation;
- FAIR enablers: list here components or characteristics that can be used as a basis to implement the sub-principle;
- FAIR challenges: list here components or characteristics that hinder, or limit the implementation of the sub-principle.

The **Example** file gives an indication about how a FAIR review can look like.

As it usually happens with FAIR self-assessments, which are interpretative and progressive processes, the example provides a screenshot of a given moment in time and it shows some limitations and uncertainties. We believe that even this aspect can have a pedagogical value.

In fact, the Example file is obsolete in some parts: some developments happened since the review. Precisely because this FAIR self-assessment allowed to make well-informed decisions and identify ways to improve the dataset's FAIRness.

Things you may read at some point

1. Time and effort required

There is no possibility to strictly evaluate the amount of time required to conduct the review. It is naturally highly dependent on the complexity of the dataset, the difficulty to collect the proper information and to correctly evaluate what FAIR implementations are feasible in a reasonable time.

If you know your data well and the infrastructure supporting it, the review of one dataset can be done in just one day. If it isn't the case and the FAIR principles require that you collect complex information in various places, it can take much longer.

Actually, it doesn't really matter: the *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* is precisely meant to be used in different manners. It can be highly detailed and technical, or sketchy and indicative, it can be done by one person in one go, or by several teams bringing their own knowledge in various rounds, etc.

There are no rules, written or not. Just read through the guidelines and complete the template in the way that best suits you, your needs and those of the users of your contents.

The self-assessment grid is essentially a tool to help you understand the FAIR principles and plan potential future actions only in a second stage.

2. Hints about FAIRness

The FAIR principles in context

FAIR principles are only principles. They are not a standard, neither a policy, nor a list of tools or technologies. It means not only that they can be contextualized, but that they necessarily have to.

The only global underlying concept of the FAIR principles is to make data and metadata easier to use and to understand both for humans and for machines. However, it is concretely more efficient to make data and metadata automatically manageable mostly by machines. In fact, a machine-actionability as extensive as possible represents the best achievement criteria for the FAIR principles' implementation.

Besides this overall goal, FAIR principles can and should be adapted to communities, data types, contextual constraints, and so on. The guidelines try to provide some of these

contextualization methods, through definitions and examples. It is then up to the data creator to identify the appropriate standards, policies, and technologies for its own case and need.

Data and publication

The FAIR principles were established with research data in mind, that is large and complex datasets, often natively digital. Hence their description follows the digital terms of “data” and “metadata”. In the context of publishing, “data” refers to the contents of the publications, textual or not. Therefore, the guidelines use the terms “data” and “content” indifferently.

Although publications can still be printed and may not be firstly defined by the digital environment, they can also be regarded as data, and even research data. To some extent, that is what means making publications FAIR: considering their “data-fication”, i.e. their transformation into data, in a more conscious and efficient way.

Digital publishing entails a series of formatting actions that effectively prepare contents for automated operations. Structured formats for publications, standard schemas for metadata, identifiers persisting throughout many websites, ISO codes for languages, are all examples of publications’ “data-fication”. They represent a formatting action of the contents and their related information that machines of the digital infrastructure will be able to manipulate and process.

Such “data-fication” will therefore increase the discoverability and reusability of the publications in the global digital environment. And this is precisely what the full review of the FAIR principles will help you to achieve in its main aspects.

The process of FAIR-ification

As mentioned before, the implementation of the FAIR principles is necessarily progressive. While the principles are rather simple in their expression, they imply a multiplicity of expertises, technologies, and concrete implementation decisions that are difficult, if not impossible, to manage at once.

The review of the FAIR principles with the analytical grid that we provide is therefore only a first step. A more comprehensive audit of the FAIR principles implementation would comprise a few more steps and take the form of a dedicated internal project.

A full FAIR-ification process can comprise three main phases: preparation, assessment, and result. The preparation step consists of a landscape study and possibly a use case analysis, containing: a review of similar or complementary recommendations (e.g., Open Science, Linked Open Data, Plan S), definitions of FAIR-compliant technologies (e.g., metadata harvesting protocols, persistent identifiers), and an analysis of current needs for the analyzed dataset.

The second phase, dedicated to the assessment, is the longest and the most detailed one. It should contextualize the FAIR generic principles according to a specific environment and, even more importantly, correctly define and describe the dataset that will be reviewed against

the FAIR principles. The full review of the dataset for each FAIR principle and sub-principle, with, in some cases, more in-depth analysis for more complicated cases can follow in a next step.

Once this assessment phase has been completed, the result phase can, (1), prioritize the FAIR possible implementations identified through the review, (2) plan for the actual implementations of the selected FAIR improvements. In some cases, this may require dedicated projects and funding, depending on the complexity of the implementations.

These are, however, only suggestions for a wider project. The *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* presented here is meant to help you conduct all the steps of the assessment phase. It tries to provide contextualisation of the FAIR principles in consideration of the publishing environment, requires to describe accurately the dataset in a summary, offers a detailed structure to conduct the review, and suggests some solutions and technologies to investigate further.

Once this work is done, you should be FAIR-aware enough to organize your own additional steps.

Unfairness of the FAIR principles?

There have been, some debates about the actual fairness of the FAIR principles. It is useful to know a bit more about these discussions to better understand the goal and logic of the FAIR principles.

A quick overview of the FAIR principles shows immediately how technical they are. This does not necessarily mean that they are complicated to understand, at least as generic principles, but it implies that they appear more genuinely neutral than they really are. It presupposes the existence and stability of advanced infrastructures that are not present for everyone everywhere. Furthermore, the concrete set-up of such infrastructures may reproduce inequities existing at a global level, if not differences of power between countries or social groups.

In addition, the alleged neutrality of technical principles leaves aside that these principles have been informed by specific actors in specific societies. Much explicitly, for instance, the [CARE principles](#), originally developed to protect indigenous data, were defined to go beyond this focus on technical aspects by promoting another set of priorities, namely: Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics. Such aspects are indeed all absent from the FAIR principles.

It is also important to note that FAIR does not mean open. The FAIR principles mention openness essentially considering components of the infrastructure, not in terms of access to the contents (in fact, “accessibility” under the FAIR principles are (re)defined in a very specific way, as is explained in the “Accessibility” section of the grid). Contents completely closed, and eventually even proprietary, can be technically perfectly FAIR. Nevertheless, FAIR principles can easily be counted as a dimension of Open Science. FAIR principles

support Open Science as they ensure, at least as a technical layer, wide discoverability and accessibility of data and metadata.

Focussing technical aspects, with a high level of trust in the infrastructure availability, and considering complex and ever-increasing research data, the FAIR principles tend to give priority to machine-actionability and big data processes. While these methods are certainly useful for many scientific operations, they should also be measured to the actual needs and means of the data providers. The objective of data and metadata fully and exhaustively machine-actionable can be, if achievable at all, an horizon, but the FAIR principles, like said before, should be more contextualized in order to envision realistic implementations.

To summarize, as valid as they are to support data management best practices and the development of Open Science, the FAIR principles can be taken with a grain of salt, especially when applied to Diamond Open Access publishing. The *FAIR Publishing Self-assessment Grid* guidelines precisely tried to include also that perspective regarding the FAIR principles implementation.

3. Additional information

Below is a list, not exhaustive, of useful tools to look into more deeply depending on your needs. Some of them are mentioned in the guidelines, others are added for information purposes. The list is meant to give an overview of the tools that can support FAIR-ification.

The links referenced here concern:

- *standards*, i.e. well-defined and extensive norms, established, accepted and implemented by groups of people, from organizations to communities: standards are a set of rules that are not always mandatory and also offer some liberty in their implementation, as only some parts of the standard may be implemented;
- *requirements*, i.e. constraints that are often related to a specific service or tool and are necessary for the service or tool to operate: the requirements are at least partially mandatory, but concern a more limited community than a standard;
- *policies*, i.e. recommendations set by official or representative bodies that usually do not give concrete implementation's solutions and remain high-level: policies can be binding in some cases, but their concrete applications may take different paths with no validation process in place to check the final result;
- *technologies*, i.e. different kinds of objects that can be used as tools to obtain certain results or as components of a process: technologies usually require a certain level of expertise to be used and are in that sense more demanding than standards, requirements, and policies.

Naturally, these types are not always clear-cut. The FAIR principles, for example, can be located somewhere between a policy and a requirement. They are a policy as they are supported by official and representative bodies and remain high-level, providing recommendations about general best practices. They are indirectly a requirement as they take into account the actual constraints of the digital environment which represent *de facto*

constraints to take full advantage of this environment. It is however useful to identify differences of status between these types, as these differences have a direct impact on the modalities of implementation.

The deliverable “Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of FAIR Principles” from the CRAFT-OA Horizon Europe project provides an extensive mapping between the FAIR principles and standards, policies, requirements, and technologies used in the digital publishing environment. The report can be found on Zenodo at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14637597>.

Standards

- Metadata
 - DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary): <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>
 - DDI Alliance Controlled Vocabulary for Data Type: <https://rdf-vocabulary.ddialliance.org/ddi-cv/DataType/1.1.2/DataType.html>
 - Dublin Core element set (first version, 15 elements): <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/>
 - Dublin Core metadata terms (second version, 55 terms including the 15 elements): <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>
 - METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard): <https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>
 - PROV-DM (Provenance Data Model): <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>
- Identifiers
 - ARK (Archival Resource Key): <https://arks.org/>
 - DOI (Digital Object identifier): <https://www.doi.org/the-identifier/what-is-a-doi/>
 - ISSN (International Standard Serial Number): <https://www.issn.org/understanding-the-issn/what-is-an-issn/>
 - ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID): <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/>
 - ROR (Research Organization Registry): <https://ror.org/>
 - VIAF (Virtual International Authority File): <https://www.oclc.org/en/viaf.html>
- Vocabularies
 - BISAC (Book Industry Standards and Communications): <https://www.bisg.org/complete-bisac-subject-headings-list>
 - European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST): <https://elsst.cessda.eu/>
 - LCSH (Library of Congress Subject Headings): <https://www.loc.gov/aba/publications/FreeLCSH/freelcsh.html#Introduction>
 - MeSH (Medical Subject Headings): <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>
- Licenses
 - Creative Commons (CC) licenses: <https://creativecommons.org/>

- GNU General Public License: <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>
- MIT license: <https://opensource.org/license/mit>
- Open Database license for data:
<https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/summary/>

Policies

- DOAS (Diamond Open Access Quality):
<https://diamasproject.eu/introducing-doas-the-benchmark-for-diamond-open-access-quality/>
- Plan S:
<https://www.coalition-s.org/addendum-to-the-coalition-s-guidance-on-the-implementation-of-plan-s/principles-and-implementation/>

Requirements

- BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine):
https://www.base-search.net/about/en/faq_oai.php
- Crossref metadata schema: <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/schema-library/>
- Datacite metadata schema: <https://schema.datacite.org/>
- DOAB (Directory of Open Access Books):
<https://www.doabooks.org/en/publishers/join-doab>
- DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals): <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>
- OpenAire guidelines for literature repositories:
<https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0/introduction.html>
- Pubmed central: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pub/addjournal/>

Technologies

- OAI-PMH (Open Archive Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting):
<https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>
- OWL (Web Ontology Language): <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>
- RDF (Resource Description Framework): <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>
- SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System): <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>
- XML (Extensible Markup Language): <https://www.w3.org/XML/>
- XML TEI (Text Encoding Initiative): <https://tei-c.org/>
- XML JATS (Journal Article Tag Suite): <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov/>

Things you can read if you really want to

- Armengou, C., Edig, X. van ., Laakso, M., & Umerle, T. (2025): CRAFT-OA Deliverable 3.1 Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of FAIR Principles (Final). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14637597>

- Avançaço, K & Gingold, A. (2022, 12 9). FAIRifying a scholarly publishing service: Methodology based on the OpenEdition's internal FAIR audit. *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 25(2) doi: [10.3998/jep.1540](https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.1540)
- EOSC interoperability framework: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1>
- GOFAIR Foundation: FAIR Implementation Profile wizard, <https://fip.fair-wizard.com>
- Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>